

Supplemental Table 2. Search strategy used for each database to identify articles that assessed the relationship between structural vulnerability factors and gestational weight gain.

Searches performed October 22nd, 2018 and updated August 1st, 2019

MEDLINE(R) ALL (Ovid, 1946 to July 30th 2019)

1. Socioeconomic Factors/ or Poverty/ or Poverty Areas/ or Social Class/ or Social Mobility/ or Educational Status/ or Literacy/ or Employment/ or Personnel Downsizing/ or Unemployment/ or Workplace/ or Income/ or Remuneration/
2. family characteristics/ or marital status/ or divorce/ or marriage/ or single parent/ or widowhood/
3. social isolation/ or social alienation/ or social marginalization/
4. Rural Health Services/ or Health Services Accessibility/ or Rural Health/ or Rural Population/
5. socioeconomic*.ti,ab,kw.
6. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (disparity or disparities)).ti,ab,kw.
7. ((social* or economic* or occupational*) adj2 (class or classes or stratification)).ti,ab,kw.
8. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (status or condition? or situation? or standing or mobility)).ti,ab,kw.
9. ((social* or economic* or financial*) adj2 (inequalit* or equalit* or securit* or insecurit*)).ti,ab,kw.
10. (food adj3 (security or insecurit* or accessibilit*)).ti,ab,kw.
11. ((education* or literacy) adj4 (level* or status or lack or insufficien* or poor or attainment)).ti,ab,kw.

12. illiteracy.ti,ab,kw.
13. (income* or remuneration* or livelihood or salary or salaries).ti,ab,kw.
14. (poverty or impoverish*).ti,ab,kw.
15. employment.ti,ab,kw.
16. Unemployment.ti,ab,kw.
17. ((single adj3 (parent* or mother* or father* or mom? or dad?)) or married or marital status or divorc* or widow*).ti,ab,kw.
18. (social* adj3 (isolation or isolated or alienat* or marginalization)).ti,ab,kw.
19. ((Lack* or inadequa* or insufficien* or depriv*) adj2 social support*).ti,ab,kw.
20. ((rural or remote* or isolated or secluded or inaccessible) adj3 (area? or region? or territor* or localit* or health service* or hospital*)).ti,ab,kw.
21. ((healthcare or health service*) adj3 access*).ti,ab,kw.
22. Vulnerable Populations/
23. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (vulnerab* or disadvantaged)).ti,ab,kw.
24. ((vulnerab* or disadvantaged) adj2 (group? or person? or population? or people or wom?n)).ti,ab,kw.
25. "Emigration and Immigration"/ or "Emigrants and Immigrants"/ or Undocumented Immigrants/ or Refugees/
26. (asylum seeker* or refugee* or immigrant*).ti,ab,kw.
27. American Native Continental Ancestry Group/ or Indians, Central American/ or Indians, North American/ or Indians, South American/ or Inuits/ or Oceanic Ancestry Group/
28. (aborigin* or first nation* or indigenous or inuit or metis or (native adj2 (person* or individual* or people*))).ti,ab,kw.

29. ethnic groups/ or Minority Groups/ or african americans/ or arabs/ or asian americans/ or hispanic americans/ or mexican americans/
30. (ethnic* or minorit*).ti,ab,kw.
31. (((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Mexican or Latin) adj2 American*) or Arab* or (afr* adj2 Caribbean) or ((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Latin) adj2 british*)).ti,ab,kw.
32. ((African or black or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Caribbean or Latin) adj2 Canadian*).ti,ab,kw.
33. prisoners/ or sex workers/ or Sex Work/ or Drug Users/
34. (prisoner* or sex work* or prostitut* or (drug? adj3 (user? or using))).ti,ab,kw.
35. violence/ or domestic violence/ or gender-based violence/ or intimate partner violence/ or spouse abuse/ or physical abuse/
36. ((violence or (domestic* or spous* or partner* or physical*)) adj3 abus*).ti,ab,kw.
37. Pregnancy in Adolescence/
38. (pregnan* adj3 (teen* or adolescen*)).ti,ab,kw.
39. 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38
40. ((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) adj3 weight?).ti,ab,kw.
41. ((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) and (weight? adj2 gain*)).ti,ab,kw.
42. 40 or 41
43. weight gain/ or body weight/

44. pregnancy/ or pregnancy, high-risk/ or exp pregnancy, multiple/ or exp pregnancy outcome/
or prenatal nutritional physiological phenomena/ or Pregnant Women/

45. 43 and 44

46. 42 or 45

47. 39 and 46

48. exp animals/ not humans/

49. 47 not 48

50. (addresses or autobiography or bibliography or biography or comment or congresses or
consensus development conference or consensus development conference, nih or dataset or
dictionary or directory or duplicate publication or editorial or government publications or
interactive tutorial or lectures or legal cases or legislation or letter or news or newspaper article
or patient education handout or periodical index or technical report or video-audio media or
webcasts).pt.

51. 49 not 50

52. limit 51 to (english or french)

Results: 4870 references retrieved

Embase (Ovid, 1947 to July 30th, 2019)

1. Socioeconomics/ or educational status/ or literacy/ or income group/ or highest income group/
or lowest income group/ or working poor/ or middle income group/ or poverty/ or social status/

or social class/ or social stratification/ or income/ or household income/ or family income/ or personal income/ or remuneration/ or "salary and fringe benefit"/ or salary/ or employment/ or employment status/ or unemployment/ or workplace/

2. family size/ or marriage/ or divorce/ or forced marriage/ or single-parent family/ or widowed person/ or widow/ or widower/

3. social isolation/ or social alienation/ or social exclusion/ or ostracism/

4. rural health care/ or rural health/ or rural population/

5. socioeconomic*.ti,ab,kw.

6. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (disparity or disparities)).ti,ab,kw.

7. ((social* or economic* or occupational*) adj2 (class or classes or stratification)).ti,ab,kw.

8. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (status or condition? or situation? or standing or mobility)).ti,ab,kw.

9. ((social* or economic* or financial*) adj2 (inequalit* or equalit* or securit* or insecurit*)).ti,ab,kw.

10. food security/ or food insecurity/

11. (food adj3 (security or insecurit* or accessibilit*)).ti,ab,kw.

12. ((education* or literacy) adj4 (level* or status or lack or insufficien* or poor or attainment)).ti,ab,kw.

13. illiteracy.ti,ab,kw.

14. (income* or remuneration* or livelihood or salary or salaries).ti,ab,kw.

15. (poverty or impoverish*).ti,ab,kw.

16. employment.ti,ab,kw.

17. Unemployment.ti,ab,kw.

18. ((single adj3 (parent* or mother* or father* or mom? or dad?)) or married or marital status or divorc* or widow*).ti,ab,kw.
19. (social* adj3 (isolation or isolated or alienat* or marginalization)).ti,ab,kw.
20. ((Lack* or inadequa* or insufficien* or depriv*) adj2 social support*).ti,ab,kw.
21. ((rural or remote* or isolated or secluded or inaccessible) adj3 (area? or region? or territor* or localit* or health service* or hospital*)).ti,ab,kw.
22. ((healthcare or health service*) adj3 access*).ti,ab,kw.
23. vulnerable population/
24. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (vulnerab* or disadvantaged)).ti,ab,kw.
25. ((vulnerab* or disadvantaged) adj2 (group? or person? or population? or people or wom?n)).ti,ab,kw.
26. migrant/ or immigrant/ or refugee/ or asylum seeker/
27. (asylum seeker* or refugee* or immigrant*).ti,ab,kw.
28. indigenous people/ or alaska native/ or american indian/ or canadian aboriginal/ or first nation/
29. asian american/ or asian continental ancestry group/ or british asian/ or black person/ or african american/ or african brazilian/ or african caribbean/ or hispanic/ or mexican american/
30. indigenous australian/ or oceanic ancestry group/ or pacific islander/ or torres strait islander/
31. "ethnic or racial aspects"/ or cultural factor/ or ethnic difference/ or ethnicity/ or minority group/
32. (aborigin* or first nation* or indigenous or inuit or metis or (native adj2 (person* or individual* or people*))).ti,ab,kw.
33. (ethnic* or minorit*).ti,ab,kw.

34. (((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Mexican or Latin) adj2 American*) or Arab* or (afr* adj2 Caribbean) or ((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Latin) adj2 british*)).ti,ab,kw.
35. ((African or black or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Caribbean or Latin) adj2 Canadian*).ti,ab,kw.
36. prisoner/ or sex worker/ or prostitution/ or "drug use"/ or "unlicensed drug use"/
37. (prisoner* or sex work* or prostitut* or (drug? adj3 (user? or using))).ti,ab,kw.
38. violence/ or dating violence/ or domestic violence/ or battered woman/ or family violence/ or partner violence/ or assault/ or battering/ or exposure to violence/ or gender based violence/ or physical violence/ or sexual violence/ or sexual abuse/ or physical abuse/
39. ((violence or (domestic* or spous* or partner* or physical*)) adj3 abus*).ti,ab,kw.
40. adolescent pregnancy/
41. (pregnan* adj3 (teen* or adolescen*)).ti,ab,kw.
42. 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41
43. gestational weight gain/
44. ((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) and (weight? adj2 gain*)).ti,ab,kw.
45. ((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) adj3 weight?).ti,ab,kw.
46. 43 or 44 or 45
47. body weight/ or weight gain/ or body weight gain/
48. pregnancy/ or unplanned pregnancy/ or unwanted pregnancy/ or high risk pregnancy/ or exp multiple pregnancy/ or exp pregnancy outcome/ or maternal nutrition/ or pregnant woman/

49. 47 and 48

50. 46 or 49

51. 42 and 50

52. exp animal/ not human/

53. 51 not 52

54. (abstract report or books or "book review" or chapter or conference abstract or conference paper or "conference review" or editorial or erratum or letter or note or patent or reports).pt.

55. 53 not 54

56. limit 55 to (english or french)

Results: 5,043 references retrieved

APA PsycInfo (Ovid, 1806 to July Week 4 2019)

1. socioeconomic status/ or family socioeconomic level/ or lower class/ or disadvantaged/ or economic security/ or "income (economic)"/ or poverty/ or income level/ or lower income level/ or middle income level/ or upper income level/ or financial strain/ or salaries/ or social class/ or lower class/ or middle class/ or upper class/ or disadvantaged/ or socioeconomic class attitudes/ or lower class attitudes/ or middle class attitudes/ or upper class attitudes/ or employment status/ or unemployment/ or social mobility/ or literacy/ or educational attainment level/
2. divorce/ or divorced persons/ or dysfunctional family/ or widowers/ or widows/ or family structure/ or parenthood status/ or family size/ or single parents/ or single fathers/ or single

mothers/ or never married/ or unwed mothers/ or parental characteristics/ or family background/
or parent educational background/ or parental occupation/

3. social isolation/ or social deprivation/ or marginalization/

4. rural environments/ or health disparities/

5. socioeconomic*.ti,ab.

6. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (disparity or disparities)).ti,ab.

7. ((social* or economic* or occupational*) adj2 (class or classes or stratification)).ti,ab.

8. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (status or condition? or situation? or standing or mobilit*)).ti,ab.

9. ((social* or economic* or financial*) adj2 (inequalit* or equalit* or securit* or
insecurit*)).ti,ab.

10. (food adj3 (security or insecurit* or accessibilit*)).ti,ab.

11. ((education* or literacy) adj4 (level* or status or lack or insufficien* or poor or
attainment)).ti,ab.

12. illiteracy.ti,ab.

13. (income* or remuneration* or livelihood or salary or salaries).ti,ab.

14. (poverty or impoverish*).ti,ab.

15. (employment or unemployment).ti,ab.

16. ((single adj3 (parent* or mother* or father* or mom? or dad?)) or married or marital status or
divorc* or widow*).ti,ab.

17. (social* adj3 (isolation or isolated or alienat* or marginalization)).ti,ab.

18. ((Lack* or inadequa* or insufficien* or depriv*) adj2 social support*).ti,ab.

19. ((rural or remote* or isolated or secluded or inaccessible) adj3 (area? or region? or territor*
or localit* or health service* or hospital*)).ti,ab.

20. ((healthcare or health service*) adj3 access*).ti,ab.
21. at risk populations/
22. ((social* or economic*) adj2 (vulnerab* or disadvantaged)).ti,ab.
23. ((vulnerab* or disadvantaged) adj2 (group? or person? or population? or people or wom?n)).ti,ab.
24. human migration/ or geographical mobility/ or immigration/ or refugees/
25. (asylum seeker* or refugee* or immigrant*).ti,ab.
26. "racial and ethnic groups"/ or african cultural groups/ or arabs/ or blacks/ or indigenous populations/ or alaska natives/ or american indians/ or inuit/ or pacific islanders/ or hawaii natives/ or "latinos/latinas"/ or mexican americans/ or minority groups/
27. (aborigin* or first nation* or indigenous or inuit or metis or (native adj2 (person* or individual* or people*))).ti,ab.
28. (ethnic* or minorit*).ti,ab.
29. (((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Mexican or Latin) adj2 American*) or Arab* or (afr* adj2 Caribbean) or ((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Latin) adj2 british*)).ti,ab.
30. ((African or black or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Caribbean or Latin) adj2 Canadian*).ti,ab.
31. drug abuse/ or prostitution/ or prisoners/
32. violence/ or domestic violence/ or intimate partner violence/ or physical abuse/ or partner abuse/ or physical abuse/
33. adolescent pregnancy/
34. (prisoner* or sex work* or prostitut* or (drug? adj3 (user? or using))).ti,ab.

35. ((violence or (domestic* or spous* or partner* or physical*)) adj3 abus*).ti,ab.
36. (pregnan* adj3 (teen* or adolescen*)).ti,ab.
37. 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36
38. ((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) adj3 weight?).ti,ab.
39. ((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) and (weight? adj2 gain*)).ti,ab.
40. 38 or 39
41. body weight/ or weight gain/
42. pregnancy/ or exp pregnancy outcomes/
43. 41 and 42
44. 40 or 43
45. 37 and 44
46. (animal not human).po.
47. 45 not 46
48. (authored book or book or dissertation abstract or edited book or encyclopedia).pt.
49. 47 not 48
50. limit 49 to (english or french)

Results: 640 references retrieved

CINAHL (EBSCOHost, 1976-2019)

#	Query	Results
S1	(MH "Socioeconomic Factors") OR (MH "Illiteracy") OR (MH "Literacy") OR (MH "Poverty") OR (MH "Social Class") OR (MH "Poverty Areas") OR (MH "Social Mobility") OR (MH "Educational Status") OR (MH "Income") OR (MH "Salaries and Fringe Benefits") OR (MH "Unemployment") OR (MH "Employment") OR (MH "Marital Status") OR (MH "Family Characteristics") OR (MH "Divorce") OR (MH "Marriage") OR (MH "Single Person") OR (MH "Single Parent") OR (MH "Widows and Widowers")	137,087
S2	(MH "Social Alienation") OR (MH "Social Isolation")	5,255
S3	(MH "Rural Health Services") OR (MH "Rural Health Centers") OR (MH "Rural Population") OR (MH "Hospitals, Rural")	9,302
S4	TI socioeconomic* OR AB socioeconomic*	18,679
S5	TI (((social* or economic*) N2 (disparity or disparities))) OR AB (((social* or economic*) N2 (disparity or disparities)))	462
S6	TI (((social* or economic* or occupational*) N2 (class or classes or stratification))) OR AB (((social* or economic* or occupational*) N2 (class or classes or stratification)))	2,281

S7	TI (((social* or economic*) N2 (status or condition? or situation? or standing or mobilit*))) OR AB (((social* or economic*) N2 (status or condition? or situation? or standing or mobilit*)))	7,342
S8	TI (((social* or economic* or financial*) N2 (inequalit* or equalit* or securit* or insecurit*))) OR AB (((social* or economic* or financial*) N2 (inequalit* or equalit* or securit* or insecurit*)))	3,696
S9	TI ((food N3 (security or insecurit* or accessibilit*))) OR AB ((food N3 (security or insecurit* or accessibilit*)))	1,709
S10	TI (((education* or literacy) N4 (level* or status or lack or insufficien* or poor or attainment))) OR AB (((education* or literacy) N4 (level* or status or lack or insufficien* or poor or attainment)))	22,875
S11	TI illiteracy OR AB illiteracy	314
S12	TI ((income* or remuneration* or livelihood or salary or salaries)) OR AB ((income* or remuneration* or livelihood or salary or salaries))	43,427
S13	TI ((poverty or impoverish*)) OR AB ((poverty or impoverish*))	8,133
S14	TI (employment or unemployment) OR AB (employment or unemployment)	19,980
S15	TI (((single N3 (parent* or mother* or father* or mom? or dad?)) or married or marital status or divorc* or widow*)) OR AB (((single N3 (parent* or mother* or father* or mom? or dad?)) or married or marital status or divorc* or widow*))	14,488

S16	TI ((social* N3 (isolation or isolated or alienat* or marginalization))) OR AB ((social* N3 (isolation or isolated or alienat* or marginalization)))	2,512
S17	TI (((Lack* or inadequa* or insufficien* or depriv*) N2 "social support*")) OR AB (((Lack* or inadequa* or insufficien* or depriv*) N2 "social support*"))	571
S18	TI (((rural or remote* or isolated or secluded or inaccessible) N3 (area? or region? or territor* or localit* or "health service*" or hospital*))) OR AB (((rural or remote* or isolated or secluded or inaccessible) N3 (area? or region? or territor* or localit* or "health service*" or hospital*)))	9,405
S19	TI (((healthcare or health service*) N3 access*) OR AB (((healthcare or health service*) N3 access*)	9,166
S20	(MH "Vulnerability")	2,995
S21	TI (((social* or economic*) N2 (vulnerab* or disadvantaged))) OR AB (((social* or economic*) N2 (vulnerab* or disadvantaged)))	1,497
S22	TI (((vulnerab* or disadvantaged) N2 (group? or person? or population? or people or wom?n))) OR AB (((vulnerab* or disadvantaged) N2 (group? or person? or population? or people or wom?n)))	5,380
S23	(MH "Immigrants") OR (MH "Immigrants, Illegal") OR (MH "Emigration and Immigration") OR (MH "Refugees")	16,442

S24	(MH "Indigenous Peoples") OR (MH "Aborigines") OR (MH "Maori") OR (MH "Eskimos") OR (MH "Native Americans") OR (MH "Blacks") OR (MH "Arabs") OR (MH "Hispanics") OR (MH "Ethnic Groups") OR (MH "Minority Groups")	75,084
S25	TI ((aborigin* or "first nation*" or indigenous or inuit or metis or (native N2 (person* or individual* or people*)))) OR AB ((aborigin* or "first nation*" or indigenous or inuit or metis or (native N2 (person* or individual* or people*))))	7,910
S26	TI ((ethnic* or minorit*)) OR AB ((ethnic* or minorit*))	43,872
S27	TI ((((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Mexican or Latin) adj2 American*) or Arab* or (afr* adj2 Caribbean) or ((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Latin) N2 british*))) OR AB ((((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Mexican or Latin) adj2 American*) or Arab* or (afr* adj2 Caribbean) or ((African or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Latin) N2 british*)))	4,596
S28	TI (((African or black or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Caribbean or Latin) N2 Canadian*)) OR AB (((African or black or Asian or Chinese or Hispanic or Caribbean or Latin) N2 Canadian*))	206
S29	(MH "Prostitution") OR (MH "Prisoners") OR (MH "Substance Abusers") OR (MH "Intravenous Drug Users")	12,431

S30	(MH "Violence") OR (MH "Dating Violence") OR (MH "Domestic Violence") OR (MH "Intimate Partner Violence") OR (MH "Exposure to Violence")	22,770
S31	(MH "Pregnancy in Adolescence") OR (MH "Maternal Age 14 and Under")	4,181
S32	TI ((prisoner* or "sex work*" or prostitut* or (drug? N3 (user? or using)))) OR AB ((prisoner* or "sex work*" or prostitut* or (drug? N3 (user? or using))))	5,415
S33	TI (((violence or (domestic* or spous* or partner* or physical*)) N3 abus*)) OR AB (((violence or (domestic* or spous* or partner* or physical*)) N3 abus*))	5,173
S34	TI ((pregnan* N3 (teen* or adolescen*))) OR AB ((pregnan* N3 (teen* or adolescen*)))	2,960
S35	S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10 OR S11 OR S12 OR S13 OR S14 OR S15 OR S16 OR S17 OR S18 OR S19 OR S20 OR S21 OR S22 OR S23 OR S24 OR S25 OR S26 OR S27 OR S28 OR S29 OR S30 OR S31 OR S32 OR S33 OR S34	347,542
S36	TI (((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) N3 weight?)) OR AB (((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) N3 weight?))	113

S37	TI (((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) and (weight? N2 gain*))) OR AB (((maternal* or pregnan* or gestational*) and (weight? N2 gain*)))	5
S38	S36 OR S37	116
S39	((MH "Pregnancy") OR (MH "Pregnancy, High Risk") OR (MH "Pregnancy, Multiple+") OR (MH "Pregnancy, Unplanned") OR (MH "Pregnancy, Unwanted") OR (MH "Prenatal Nutritional Physiology") OR (MH "Pregnancy Complications") OR (MH "Expectant Mothers")) AND ((MH "Body Weight") OR (MH "Body Weight Changes") OR (MH "Weight Gain")))	2,199
S40	S38 OR S39	2,292
S41	S35 AND S40	560
S42	(MH "Animals") NOT (MH "Human")	30,484
S43	S41 NOT S42	559
S44	S41 NOT S42	548
S45	(ZT "advertisement") or (ZT "advertising review") or (ZT "algorithm") or (ZT "anecdote") or (ZT "announcement") or (ZT "architecture review") or (ZT "art reproduction") or (ZT "bibliography") or (ZT "biography") or (ZT "book") or (ZT "book chapter") or (ZT "book review") or (ZT "calendar") or (ZT "care plan") or (ZT "cartoon") or (ZT "cartoon/comic strip") or (ZT "commentary") or (ZT "computer program") or (ZT	683,068

	<p>"conference paper") or (ZT "conference proceeding") or (ZT "consumer/patient") or (ZT "consumer/patient teaching") or (ZT "consumer/patient teaching materials") or (ZT "course review") or (ZT "cover art") or (ZT "critical path") or (ZT "directories") or (ZT "directory") or (ZT "dissertation") or (ZT "doctoral dissertation") or (ZT "editorial") or (ZT "entertainment review") or (ZT "establishment review") or (ZT "exhibition review") or (ZT "festival review") or (ZT "film review") or (ZT "film/television criticism") or (ZT "form") or (ZT "forms") or (ZT "front cover") or (ZT "game/puzzle") or (ZT "games") or (ZT "glossary") or (ZT "government documents") or (ZT "historical material") or (ZT "legal case") or (ZT "lesson plan") or (ZT "letter") or (ZT "letter to the editor") or (ZT "masters thesis") or (ZT "music review") or (ZT "newspaper") or (ZT "nurse practice acts") or (ZT "obituary") or (ZT "opinion") or (ZT "practice guidelines") or (ZT "proceeding") or (ZT "proceedings") or (ZT "product review") or (ZT "teaching materials") or (ZT "television review")</p>	
S46	S44 NOT S45	522

Results: 634 references retrieved

Sociological Abstracts (Proquest, 1904 to 2019)

((((MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Low Income Groups") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Standard of Living") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Income Inequality") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Income") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Salaries") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Low Income Areas"))) OR (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Class Differences") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Mobility") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Disadvantaged") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Stratification") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Socioeconomic Factors") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Factors") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Inequality") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Sociocultural Factors") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Socioeconomic Status") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Sociodemographic Factors") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Conditions") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Class")))) OR ((MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Alienation") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social Isolation"))) OR (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Rural Poverty") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Ruralization") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Rurality") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Rural Population") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Rural Areas") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Rural Communities"))) OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Vulnerability"))) OR (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Undocumented Immigrants") OR (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Migrants") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Migration") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Immigration") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Ethnicity") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Refugees") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Immigrants") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Foreigners") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Asylum")))) OR ((MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Disadvantaged") OR

MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Poverty")) OR (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Aboriginal Australians")
OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("American Indians") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Ethnic
Groups") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Eskimos") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Ethnic
Relations") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Indigenous Populations") OR
MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Foreigners")) OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Literacy") OR
(MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Black Community") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Ethnic
Neighborhoods") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Ethnic Groups") OR
MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Blacks") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Minority Groups"))) OR
(MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Prostitution") OR (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Abuse") OR
MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Violence") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Family Violence"))) OR
(MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Battered Women") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Sexual Abuse")
OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Spouse Abuse")) OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Prisoners"))
OR (noft(socioeconomic*) OR noft(((social* OR economic*) NEAR/2 (disparity OR
disparities))) OR noft(((social* OR economic* OR occupational*) NEAR/2 (class OR classes
OR stratification))) OR noft(((social* OR economic*) NEAR/2 (status OR condition? OR
situation? OR standing OR mobil*) OR noft(((social* OR economic* OR financial*)
NEAR/2 (inequalit* OR equalit* OR securit* OR insecurit*)))) OR (noft((food NEAR/3
(security OR insecurit* OR accessibilit*))) OR noft(((education* OR literacy) NEAR/4 (level*
OR status OR lack OR insufficien* OR poor OR attainment))) OR noft(illiteracy) OR
noft((income* OR remuneration* OR livelihood OR salary OR salaries)) OR noft((poverty OR
impoverish*)) OR (noft(employment OR Unemployment) OR noft(((single NEAR/3 (parent*
OR mother* OR father* OR mom? OR dad?)) OR married OR marital status OR divorc* OR
widow*)) OR noft((social* NEAR/3 (isolation OR isolated OR alienat* OR marginalization)))

OR noft(((Lack* OR inadequa* OR insufficien* OR depriv*) NEAR/2 social support*)) OR
noft(((rural OR remote* OR isolated OR secluded OR inaccessible) NEAR/3 (area? OR region?
OR territory OR localit* OR "health service" OR hospital)))) OR (noft(((healthcare OR "health
service") NEAR/3 access*)) OR noft(((social* OR economic*) NEAR/2 (vulnerab* OR
disadvantaged))) OR noft(((vulnerab* OR disadvantaged) NEAR/2 (group? OR person? OR
population? OR people OR wom?n)))) OR noft(("asylum seeker*" OR refugee* OR immigrant*))
OR noft((aborigin* OR first nation* OR indigenous OR inuit OR metis OR (native NEAR/2
(person* OR individual* OR people*)))) OR (noft((ethnic* OR minorit*)) OR noft((((African
OR Asian OR Chinese OR Hispanic OR Mexican OR Latin) NEAR/2 American*) OR Arab*
OR (afr* NEAR/2 Caribbean) OR ((African OR Asian OR Chinese OR Hispanic OR Latin)
NEAR/2 british*))) OR noft(((African OR black OR Asian OR Chinese OR Hispanic OR
Caribbean OR Latin) NEAR/2 Canadian*)) OR noft((prisoner* OR sex work* OR prostitut* OR
(drug? NEAR/3 (user? OR using)))) OR noft(((violence OR (domestic* OR spous* OR partner*
OR physical*) NEAR/3 abus*))) OR noft((pregnan* NEAR/3 (teen* OR adolescen*))) AND
((MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Pregnancy") AND MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Body Weight")) OR
(noft(((maternal* OR pregnan* OR gestational*) NEAR/3 weight?)) OR noft(((maternal* OR
pregnan* OR gestational*) AND (weight? NEAR/2 gain*))))))

Results: 195 references retrieved